

COMPATIBILITY OF *Bacillus subtilis* WITH DIFFERENT NOVEL FUNGICIDES USED AGAINST PLANT PATHOGENS

Varsha Awasthi,¹ R.K.S. Tiwari,² V.K. Nirmalkar,³ Ganga Ram⁴ and Hitesh Pawle⁵

ABSTRACT

Bacillus species are known for their broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity and have gained significant interest as bio-control agents in agriculture. Now a day's use of new chemicals for crop management is also governing the growth and performance of bioagents. Having a tolerant strain with all desirable characters, its multiplication and application is a limiting factor for use of biocontrol agents. An experiment was conducted during 2022-2023 at laboratory of Plant Pathology, Barrister Thakur Chhedilal College of Agriculture and Research Station, Bilaspur, Indira Gandhi Krishi Vishwavidyalaya, Raipur (Chhattisgarh) to study the compatibility of *Bacillus subtilis* with different novel fungicides used against plant pathogens under *in vitro* condition. The compatibility of fungicides at five different concentrations with *B. subtilis* was studied and it was found that Carbendazim 50% WP, Azoxystrobin 25% SC, Propiconazole 10.7% + Tricyclazole 34.2% SE, Azoxystrobin 18.2% + Difenconazole 11.4% SC, Tebuconazole 50% + Trifluoxystrobin 25% WG, Trifloxystrobin 25% WG, Fosetyl Al 80% WP and Azoxystrobin 18.2% + Cyproconazole 7.3% W/W were found highly compatible with *B. subtilis* at all concentrations (100, 500, 1000, 1500, 2000 ppm) and recorded higher number of colony forming units (CFU's) and can be used under the field condition for the control of soil borne and foliar diseases. Whereas, Azoxystrobin 7.1% + Propiconazole 11.9% SE and Fluxapyroxad 6.25% + Epoxiconazole 6.25% SC were found inhibitory at higher concentrations (1000, 1500 and 2000 ppm). Fungicides i.e. Hexaconazole 50% SC, Mancozeb 75% WP, Carbendazim 12% + Mancozeb 63% WP, Chlorothalonil 75% WP and Picoxystrobin 7.05% + Propiconazole 11.9% SE were completely inhibitory even at 100 ppm concentration. Moreover, Azoxystrobin 25% W/W followed by Fosetyl Al 80% WP and Carbendazim 75% WP were found to be highly compatible with *Bacillus subtilis* and had higher colony forming units (CFU's) which were at par with control at 100 and 500 ppm concentration.

(Key words: Fungicides, *Bacillus subtilis*, pathogens and bioagent)

INTRODUCTION

Bacillus subtilis is an antagonistic bacterial biological agent which controls many air borne, seed borne and soil borne diseases (Akhond *et al.*, 2016). Extensive research indicates that the effects of *Bacillus subtilis* on plant disease suppression through various mechanisms including antibiosis, hyphallysis of pathogens, competition for nutrients and space. Moreover, it has been found that *Bacillus subtilis* can induce systemic resistance (ISR) in plants enhancing their ability to defend against diseases (Cao *et al.*, 2011; Yu *et al.*, 2011; Li *et al.*, 2013). The genus *Bacillus* is classified in the order Eubacteriales and family Bacillaceae. *Bacillus subtilis* was initially discovered by Ehrenberg in 1835 and was initially referred to as *Vibrio subtilis*. However, it was renamed by Cohin 1872. *Bacillus subtilis* is a gram-positive, rod-shaped bacterium with peritrichous flagella and the ability to form spore (Thakur *et al.*, 2022). It has ability to form a tough protective endospore

and resistance to extreme conditions (Zhou *et al.*, 2014). *Bacillus* species are known for their broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity and have gained significant interest as bio-control agents in agriculture (Nirmalkar *et al.*, 2018). Now a day's use of new chemicals for crop management is also governing the growth and performance of bioagents. Having a tolerant strain with all desirable characters, its multiplication and application is a limiting factor for use of bio-control agents (Nirmalkar *et al.*, 2020).

The combination of biological control agents with fungicides would result in disease suppression that is comparable to that obtained with more fungicide use (Sharma *et al.*, 2021). With this literature as background, studies were carried out to find the compatibility test of commonly used nineteen fungicides with *Bacillus subtilis* (effective strain BS9) at different concentrations i.e. 100, 500, 1000, 1500 and 2000 ppm using poison food technique under *in vitro* condition.

1, 4 & 5. P.G. Students, Dept. of Plant Pathology, BTC CARS, Bilaspur, IGKV Raipur, (C.G.)

2. Principal Scientist, Dept. of Plant Pathology, BTC CARS, Bilaspur, IGKV Raipur, (C.G.)

3. Scientist, Dept. of Plant Pathology, BTC CARS, (I.G.K.V.) Raipur, (C.G.)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Poisoned food technique

The compatibility of commonly used fungicides that are usually applied for disease management was tested against most effective isolates BS9 following poison food technique. A total of different concentrations (100, 500, 1000, 1500 and 2000 ppm) of each fungicide were taken into study. Fungicides like Hexaconazole 50% SC, Carbendazim 75% WP, Mancozeb 75 %WP, Azoxystrobin 25 % SC, Propiconazole 10.7 % + Tricyclazole 34.2 % SE, Azoxystrobin 18.2% + Difenconazole 11.4% SC, Tebuconazole 50%+ Trifluoxystrobin 25% WG, Carbendazim 12%+ Mancozeb 63 % WP, Chlorothaonil 75% WP, Trifloxystrobin 25% WG, Difenconazole 25% EC, Picoxystrobin 7.05% + Propiconazole 11.7 % SC, Fosetyl Al 80 %WP, Copper oxychloride 50% WP, Cyproconazole 800 WG, Azoxystrobin 7.1% + Propiconazole 11.9% SE, Pyroclostrobin 20% WG, Fluxapyroxad 6.25% + Epoxiconazole 6.25% EC and Azoxystrobin 18.2%+Cyproconazole 7.3% W/V were tested. First, stock solutions of fungicides were prepared and then different concentrations of each fungicide were prepared simply by pipetting the required volume from the stock and adding to the sterilized nutrient agar (NA) medium just before pouring to petri dishes. The pour plate method was used to inoculate with the freshly cultured *Bacillus* strains on fungicides amended NA plates and incubated at 28±2°C for 48 hours. Nutrient agar plates without any fungicide were kept as control plates. Three replications were maintained for every concentration of individual fungicide.

Estimation of total bacterial count = No. of CFUs × Reciprocal of dilution factor

Observations recorded- CFU's were observed after 72 hours

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data regarding compatibility test of commonly used nineteen fungicides with *Bacillus subtilis* (effective strain BS9) at different concentrations i.e. 100, 500, 1000, 1500 and 2000 ppm using poison food technique under *in vitro* condition are given below.

100 ppm

Maximum colony forming units (CFU ml⁻¹) recorded at 100 ppm concentrations after 72 hours of incubation in most of the fungicides except Hexaconazole 50% SC, Mancozeb 75% WP, Carbendazim 12% + Mancozeb 63%, Chlorothaonil 75% WP, Picoxystrobin 7.05% + Propiconazole 11.71% SC and Copper oxychloride 50% WP. However, fungicides i.e. Fosetyl Al 80% WP (181.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹) followed by Propiconazole 10.7% + Tricyclazole 34.2% SE (175.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹), Azoxystrobin 18.2% + Difenconazole @11.4% SC (169.0× 10⁸ CFUs/ml), Azoxystrobin 18.2% +Cyproconazole 7.3%W/V (162.0×10⁸CFU ml⁻¹), Azoxystrobin 25 % SC (161.0×10⁸CFU ml⁻¹) and Difenconazole 25 % EC (155.0×10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹) were either non inhibitory of less

inhibitory to the growth of *Bacillus subtilis* and found highly compatible showing higher number of colony forming units (CFU's) as compared to other fungicides.

500 ppm

Maximum colony forming units (CFU ml⁻¹) recorded at 500 ppm concentrations after 72 hours of incubation in most of the fungicides i.e. Fosetyl Al 80 %WP (180.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹) followed by Propiconazole 10.7 % + Tricyclazole 34.2 % SE (175.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹), Azoxystrobin 18.2% + Difenconazole 11.4% SC (165.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹), Azoxystrobin 25 % SC (160.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹), Difenconazole 25% EC (148.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹) and Trifloxystrobin 25% WG (146.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹) and these were either non inhibitory or less inhibitory to the growth of *Bacillus subtilis* and found highly compatible showing higher number of colony forming units (CFU's) as compared to other fungicides. Whereas, fungicides i.e. Carbendazim 75 WP (137.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹), Tebuconazole 50%+ Trifluoxystrobin 25% WG (132.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹) and Azoxystrobin 18.2% + Cyproconazole 7.3%W/V (128.0×10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹) showing moderate inhibitory effect on the growth of *Bacillus subtilis*. While, fungicides i.e. Cyproconazole 800 %WG (50.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹), Pyroclostrobin 20%WG (91.2× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹) and Fluxapyroxad 6.25% + Epoxiconazole 6.25% EC (95.6× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹) were least compatible with *Bacillus subtilis* over control (200.0×10⁸) CFU ml⁻¹.

1000 ppm

Maximum colony forming units (CFU ml⁻¹) recorded at 1000 ppm concentrations after 72 hours of incubation in most of the fungicides i.e. Trifluoxystrobin 25% WG (140.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹) followed by Azoxystrobin 18.2% + Cyproconazole 7.3% W/V (128.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹), Trifloxystrobin 25% WG (127.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹) and Carbendazim 75 WP (123.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹) were either non inhibitory or less inhibitory to the growth of *Bacillus subtilis* and found highly compatible showing higher number of colony forming units (CFU's) as compared to other fungicides. While, fungicides i.e. Fluxapyroxad 6.25% + Epoxiconazole 6.25% EC (22.6× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹), Difenconazole 25% EC (42.6× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹) and Azoxystrobin 7.1% + Propiconazole 11.9% SE (81.3 × 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹) were least compatible with *Bacillus subtilis* over control (179.0×10⁸) CFU ml⁻¹.

1500 ppm

Maximum colony forming units (CFU ml⁻¹) recorded at 1500 ppm concentrations after 72 hours of incubation in most of the fungicides i.e. Azoxystrobin 18.2% + Difenconazole 11.4% SC (125.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹) followed by Trifloxystrobin 25% WG (124.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹) and Azoxystrobin 25 % SC (117.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹) and these were either non inhibitory of less inhibitory for the growth of *Bacillus subtilis* and found highly compatible showing higher number of colony forming units (CFU's) as compared to other fungicides. Whereas, fungicides i.e. Fosetyl Al 80 %WP (113.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹) and Azoxystrobin 18.2% + Cyproconazole 7.3%W/V (110.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹), Carbendazim 75 WP (106.0× 10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹) showed moderate inhibitory

effect on the growth of *Bacillus subtilis*. While, fungicides i.e. Fluxapyroxad 6.25% + Epoxiconazole 6.25% EC (25.3×10^8 CFU ml⁻¹), Azoxystrobin 7.1% + propiconazole 11.9% SE (27.0×10^8 CFU ml⁻¹) and Pyroclostrobin 20% WG (29.3×10^8 CFU ml⁻¹) were least compatible with *Bacillus subtilis* over control (183.0×10^8 CFU ml⁻¹).

2000 ppm

Maximum colony forming units (CFU ml⁻¹) recorded at 2000 ppm concentrations after 72 hours of incubation in most of the fungicides i.e. Azoxystrobin 25 % W/W (130.0×10^8 CFU ml⁻¹) followed by Fosetyl Al 80 % WP (128.0×10^8 CFU ml⁻¹) and Carbendazim 75 WP (122.0×10^8 CFU ml⁻¹) and these were either non inhibitory or less inhibitory for the growth of *Bacillus subtilis* and found highly compatible showing higher number of colony forming unit (CFU's) as compared to other fungicides. Whereas, fungicides i.e. Azoxystrobin 18.2% + Cyproconazole 7.3% W/V (107.0×10^8 CFU ml⁻¹), Trifloxystrobin 25% WG (102.0×10^8 CFU ml⁻¹) and Azoxystrobin 18.2% + Difenconazole 11.4% SC (92.0×10^8 CFU ml⁻¹) showed moderate inhibitory effect on the growth of *Bacillus subtilis*. While, fungicides Propiconazole 10.7 % + Tricyclazole 34.2 % SE (75.3×10^8 CFU ml⁻¹) and Tebuconazole 50%+ Trifluoxystrobin 25% WG (86.3×10^8 CFU ml⁻¹) were found least compatible with *Bacillus subtilis* over control (181.0×10^8 CFU ml⁻¹).

Colony forming units (CFU's) recorded from

different concentrations of fungicides indicates that most of the fungicides Carbendazim 50% WP, Azoxystrobin 25% SC, Propiconazole 10.7% + Tricyclazole 34.2% SE, Azoxystrobin 18.2% + Difenconazole 11.4% SC, Tebuconazole 50% + Trifluoxystrobin 25% WG, Trifloxystrobin 25% WG, Fosetyl Al 80% WP and Azoxystrobin 18.2% + Cyproconazole 7.3% W/V were observed to be compatible with *Bacillus subtilis* and recorded higher number of colony forming units (CFU's). Whereas, Azoxystrobin 7.1% + Propiconazole 11.9% SE, Fluxapyroxad 6.25 % + Epoxiconazole 6.25% SC and Pyroclostrobin 20% WG were found to be less compatible with *Bacillus subtilis*. Hexaconazole 50% SC, Mancozeb 75% WP, Carbendazim 12% + Mancozeb 63%, Chlorothaonil 75% WP, Picoxystrobin 7.05% + Propiconazole 11.71% SC and Copper oxychloride 50% WP were completely inhibitory even at 100 ppm concentration. Moreover, Azoxystrobin 25% W/W followed by Fosetyl Al 80% WP and Carbendazim 75% WP were found to be highly compatible with *Bacillus subtilis* and showed higher number of CFU's. Vijaykrishna *et al.* (2011) studied the compatibility of *Bacillus subtilis* strain MBI 600 with various fungicides and observed that the strain showed good compatibility with Carbendazim and Azoxystrobin at a lower concentration of 500 ppm. Similarly, Devi and Prakasam (2013) also reported the compatibility nature of Azoxystrobin 25 SC with *Pseudomonas fluorescens* and *Bacillus subtilis* at 50, 100 and 250 ppm concentrations.

Table 1. Compatibility of *Bacillus* spp. with different fungicides

Treatments	100 ppm	500 ppm	1000 ppm	1500 ppm	2000 ppm
	72 hours				
T ₁ Hexaconazole 50% SC	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
T ₂ Carbendazim 75 WP	138.0×10^8	137.0×10^8	123.0×10^8	106.0×10^8	122.0×10^8
T ₃ Mancozeb 75 WP	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
T ₄ Azoxystrobin 25 % SC	161.0×10^8	160.0×10^8	113.0×10^8	117.0×10^8	130.0×10^8
T ₅ Propiconazole 10.7 % + Tricyclazole 34.2 % SE	175.0×10^8	175.0×10^8	111.0×10^8	95.0×10^8	75.3×10^8
T ₆ Azoxystrobin 18.2% + Difenconazole 11.4% SC	169.0×10^8	165.0×10^8	119.0×10^8	125.0×10^8	92.0×10^8
T ₇ Tebuconazole 50%+ Trifluoxystrobin 25% WG	145.0×10^8	132.0×10^8	140.0×10^8	103.0×10^8	86.3×10^8
T ₈ Carbendazim 12%+ Mancozeb 63 % WP	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
T ₉ Chlorothaonil 75% WP	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
T ₁₀ Trifloxystrobin 25% WG	153.0×10^8	146.0×10^8	127.0×10^8	124.0×10^8	102.0×10^8
T ₁₁ Difenconazole 25% EC	155.0×10^8	148.0×10^8	42.6×10^8	0.0	0.0
T ₁₂ Picoxystrobin 7.05% + Propiconazole 11.7 % SC	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
T ₁₃ Fosetyl Al 80 %WP	181.0×10^8	180.0×10^8	115.0×10^8	113.0×10^8	128.0×10^8
T ₁₄ Copper oxychloride 50% WP	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
T ₁₅ Cyproconazole 800 WG	148.0×10^8	50.0×10^8	0.0	0.0	0.0
T ₁₆ Azoxystrobin 7.1% + propiconazole 11.9% SE	140.0×10^8	123.0×10^8	81.3×10^8	27.0×10^8	0.0
T ₁₇ Pyroclostrobin 20% WG	110.0×10^8	91.2×10^8	109.0×10^8	29.3×10^8	0.0
T ₁₈ Fluxapyroxad 6.25% + Epoxiconazole 6.25% EC	100.0×10^8	95.6×10^8	22.6×10^8	25.3×10^8	0.0
T ₁₉ Azoxystrobin 18.2% + Cyproconazole 7.3% W/V	162.0×10^8	128.0×10^8	128.0×10^8	110.0×10^8	107.0×10^8
T ₂₀ Control	199.0×10^8	200.0×10^8	179.0×10^8	183.0×10^8	181.0×10^8

Azoxystrobin + Difenoconazole
Figure 1 (a). Compatibility of *Bacillus* spp. with different fungicides CFU's after 72 hours

Azoxystrobin + Cyproconazole
Figure 1 (b). Compatibility of *Bacillus* spp. with different fungicides CFU's after 72 hours

REFERENCES

- Akond, M.A., F.T. Zohora, S.N. Jolly, S. Mubassara, M.A. Hossain, and R. Noor, 2016. Isolation of a potential antifungal *Bacillus subtilis* 37-JM07 strain from straw and its biocontrol efficacy to combat green mold disease of commercial mushroom, *Pleurotus ostreatus*. Environ. Sci. An Indian J. **12**(1): 23-33.
- Cao, Y., Z.H. Zhang, N. Ling, Y.J. Yuan, X.Y. Zheng, B.A. Shen, Q.R. Shen, 2011. *Bacillus subtilis* SQR9 can control *Fusarium* wilt in cucumber by colonizing plant roots. Biol. Fert. Soils. **47**:495-506.
- Devi, P.A. and V. Prakasam, 2013. Compatibility nature of Azoxystrobin 25 SC with *Pseudomonas fluorescens* and *Bacillus subtilis* on chili plants. World J. Agric. Sci. **1**(8): 258-264.
- Li, S., N. Zhang, Z. Zhang, J. Luo, B. Shen, R. Zhang, and Q. Shen, 2013. Antagonist *Bacillus subtilis* HJ5 controls *Verticillium* wilt of cotton by root colonization and bio formation. Biol. Fert. Soils, **49**:295-303.
- Nirmalkar, V. K., R. K. S. Tiwari and S. Singh, 2018. Efficacy of bio-agents against damping off in solanaceous crops under nursery conditions. Int. J. Pl. Prot. **11** (1): 1-9.
- Nirmalkar, V. K., R. K. S. Tiwari and N. Lakpale, 2020. Efficacy of different carbon and nitrogen sources against mycelial growth and sporulation of *Beauveria bassiana* and *Metarhizium anisopliae*. J. Soils and Crops, **30** (2):206-2012.
- Sharma, P., L. C. Bora, and P. Bora, 2021. *In-vitro* evaluation of population dynamics of *Pseudomonas fluorescens* in suppression of bacterial blight of rice (*Xanthomonas oryzae* ssp. *oryzae*) enriched with micronutrients. J. Soils and Crops, **31**(2):219-224.
- Thakur, Pragya, R. K. S. Tiwari, V. K. Nirmalkar, S. K. Verma, and N. K. Chaur, 2022. Antagonistic activity and Bioefficacy of *Bacillus subtilis* against Sheath Blight of Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*. Biol. Forum Int. J. **14**(3): 1305-1311.
- Vijaykrishna, K., M. S. Reddy, J. W. Kloepper, S. Yellareddygar, K. S. Lawrence, X. G. Zhou, H. Sudini, M. E. Miller, P. Appa Rao, E. Reddy Surendranatha, S. R. Niranjana and Nayaka Chandra, 2011. Plant growth-promoting activities of *Bacillus subtilis* strain 600 (integral) and its compatibility with commonly used fungicides in rice sheath blight management. Int. J. Microbiol. Res. **3** (2): 120-130.
- Yu, X., C. Ai, L. Xin and G. Zhou, 2011. The siderophore-producing bacterium, *Bacillus subtilis* CAS15, has a biocontrol effect on *Fusarium* wilt and promotes the growth of pepper. Eur. J. Soil Biol. **47**(2):138-145.
- Zhou, J.Y. X. Y. Zhao and C. C. Dai, 2014. Antagonistic mechanisms of endophytic *Pseudomonas fluorescens* against *Athelia rolfsii*. J. Appl. Microbiol. **117**(4):1144-1158.

Rec. on 20.07.2023 & Acc. on 08.08.2023